

Effect of Trade Liberalization and Manufacturing Sector on Economic Growth in Nigeria

*Obiukwu, Nwanyiola, Nwosu, Chinedu A., Chukwu, Immaculata C.
Department of Economics, Alvan Ikoku University of Education, Owerri*

ABSTRACT

The study focused on the effect of trade liberalization and manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria. Time series variables on Real GDP, Manufacturing rate, Exchange rate, Trade openness, Balance of trade, Import and Export spanning from 1981 to 2018 was utilized to estimate an OLS regression. The result indicates the existence of long-run cointegrating relationship among the variables. The ECM term shows that deviation from long-run equilibrium is corrected up to 59 percent annually. Based on the result, we recommend that there is the need to ensure that the channels of trade liberalization and manufacturing sector productivity induced growth are built around effective systems and that the policy institutions are actively involved in making systemic checks and appropriate policy innovations to ensure trade liberalization and manufacturing productivity sector led economic growth. We also recommend that the relevant regulatory agencies in the exchange rate market should be focused on enhancing the efficiency and transparency of the market in order to improve investor's confidence.

Keywords: *trade liberalization, manufacturing, economic growth*

1. INTRODUCTION

The link between trade openness and economic growth in emerging nations has generated a lot of debate among policymakers and economists over the past few decades. It has been found that trade has served as an important growth engine for countries at various stages of development, not only by helping to more efficiently allocate resources within the countries, but also by transferring growth from one region of the world to another. The General Agreement on Trade and Tariffs (GATT), which was established in 1947 following the Second World War, marked the beginning of trade liberalization. 25 nations, 12 of which are industrialized and 11 of which are developing, negotiated the GATT in 1947 with the express purpose of lowering trade barriers. In 1994, the WTO (World Trade Organization) took over as GATT's successor. Basically, trade liberalization's principal goal is to enable nations to export goods and services that they cannot manufacture effectively at home. The concept of comparative advantage is at the foundation of conventional interpretations of commerce as "the engine of growth" and the influence of trade on economic development. In essence, the free trade theories associated with David Ricardo and John Stuart Mills in the nineteenth century are what gave rise to the theory of comparative advantage. These trade theories were later modified by the factor proportion theory of Heckscher-Ohlin (1993), Stolper-Samuelson (1941), and Rubzriski (1955) trade theories.

Nigeria has gradually opened its borders to international trade and now imports a significant amount of products and services. For instance, non-imports grade increased from a mean value of N36.55 billion, representing 96.8% of total imports into Nigeria between 1970 and 1979, to N118.36 billion, 93.4% of total imports during the years 1980 through 1989, N3.48 trillion for the years 1990 through 1999, 79.9% of total import demand, and N19.33 trillion, 82.0% of total import demand between 2000 and 2008. At the end of 2014, Nigeria's imports of goods and services were \$85,354,940,000 USD. Similar to this, Nigeria's export increased by roughly 9.9% on an annual basis to N747,760 million in the last quarter of 2016, only to fall by 1% to

N2,309 million in the third quarter of 2017. The primary destinations for the nation's exports were India, the USA, France, and Spain. Between 1981 and 2016, Nigerian exports totaled an average of N370,305.54 million, with a record high of N264,881.76 million in December 2011 and a record low of N322.93 million in February 1983. Oil and natural gas make up the majority of Nigeria's exports, which make up over 90% of all export commerce. About 43% of all sales in 2014 were made in Europe, 29% in Asia, 13% in America, and 12% in Africa.

Given these significant commerce (imports and exports) volumes throughout time and the slow development seen over the previous five decades of Nigeria's political history, the yearly growth rate from 1980 to 2015 averaged 4.3%.

The link between trade liberalization and manufacturing firms has been theorized theoretically and experimentally shown to favorably affect the rate of economic growth (Sakyi, 2018). This is so that consumer surplus might arise, in his view, in an environment of price competition and product diversification. Gains from specialization and efficiency are benefits of trade liberalization (Ersoy and Derus, 2011). Nigerians adopted this economic trend and joined international and regional trade organizations like the World Trade Organization (WTO), Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), etc. after taking this trend into consideration. The goal of this economic alliance is to lower tariffs, abolish trade restrictions, and implement trade policies that are more globally focused. Despite all of her attempts to comply with these economic partnerships' objectives, such as opening up her border, Nigeria still lags behind its trade partners in terms of industrial production and overall GDP growth.

This situation creates a lot of worries and concern as manufactured goods should constitute a greater proportion of Nigeria's trade. This study therefore aims at determining performance level of Nigeria manufacturing sector in a liberalized trade economy and assess its competitive advantage in international trade. The study will also investigate how institutions, structures and policies enhances manufacturing sectors in the economy.

Examining how much trade liberalization has impacted economic performance through the manufacturing sector has become very important. The objective of this study therefore is to investigate the effect of trade liberalization and manufacturing sector on Nigeria's economic performance. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: following section one, introduction, section two focused on literature review, section three handles the methodology of the study while section 4 presents results and its analysis. Section five is devoted to result discussion while section six concludes the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Trade Liberalization and Trade Policy in Nigeria

According to Okpoko (2005), trade liberalization is measured by the proportion of international trade to a country's GDP. This implies that trade has a greater influence on the domestic economy if openness index is high. Atoyebi (2012) argued that the removal of trade barriers (openness) is strongly and favorably correlated with the GDP-growth rate. Utikulu and Ozdemir (2004), however, believe that while openness and trade can boost economic growth in some nations, it can also have the opposite effect in others, depending on the level of development of the individual nation.

The earliest form of liberalizing trade prior to the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) is the import substitution policies in the 1970s (Olaifa, Subair and Biala, 2013). They observed that the policy did not record much success as a result of unconducive macroeconomic environment. The adoption of SAP in 1986, however brought the emergence of trade liberalization which was accompanied by the elimination of foreign exchange control to reflect economic realities, removal of price control and disbandment of commodity boards. The policy thrust of SAP in Nigeria was to create an environment conducive for enhanced increase in capital flows,

transfers, adoption of appropriate technologies and increase the share of trade revenue to government as another means of reducing the total dependence of the economy on oil revenue. The economic indicators as reported by World Bank Development indicators (2013) showed that trade as a percentage of GDP per capita rose during the pre-liberalization period but increased significantly in the post liberalization period. Although access to specific markets -judged by their size and growth is important, domestic market factors are predictably less relevant in export-oriented foreign firms (Ademola, Oluseyi, Ibiyemi and Babatunde, 2013). A range of survey suggests a widespread perception that “open economies” encourage more foreign investment which happens to be what the domestic economy needs to grow.

One good indicator of openness is the relative size of the export sector. As Singh and Jun (1995) study indicated, exports particularly manufacturing exports are a significant determinant of FDI flows and their study showed that there is a strong evidence that exports precede FDI flows. They observe that china in particular, has for this reason attracted much FDI into its export sector, in Bangladesh, on the other hand, foreign investors have been attracted to the manufacturing sector by its lack of quota for textiles and clothing exports to European Union and the US markets.

2.2 Proponents of Trade Liberalization

This is the basic underlying trade reforms that involve extensive liberalization of trade and investment barriers, unification of tariff rates and domestic tax rates, removal of consumption and production subsidies and deregulation of industry and privatization of state owned enterprises. It is the primary philosophy behind World Bank loans to facilitate restructuring and IMF lending packages that requires micro-economic structural reform. It is also very old idea going back to Adam Smith theory of absolute advantage and David Ricardo theory of comparative advantage but its modern translation into trade liberalization largely begin with the reform in Chile in the 1970's advocated by the “Chicago school of Economics”. They argued that policies that make an economy open to trade and investment with the rest of the world are needed for sustained economic growth. In support, Dollar and Acrt (2001) posited that, no country in recent decades has achieved economic success, in terms of substantial increase in living standards for its people, without being open to the rest of the world. This has been an important element in the economic success of East Asia where the average import tariff has fallen from 30 percent to 10 over the twenty years.

Trade liberalization enhances specialization on goods a country has comparative advantage on, which tends to lower cost and brings about varieties of consumer goods, thus increasing consumer surplus and creating more satisfaction. The proponents contend that when an economy is open, there will be more intense competition which obliges local firms to operate more efficiently than under protection.

2.3 History of Nigeria Manufacturing Sector

It has been argued that technological innovation, enterprise development, and industrial capacity—rather than a country's level of endowed material resources or its vast human resources—are the fastest trends through which a country can achieve sustainable economic growth and development (Adeola, 2005). In the modern world, a country's manufacturing sector is used to gauge its economic performance (Amakom, 2012).

Nigerian manufacturing sector is as old as Nigeria economy itself. Before independence, agricultural production dominated Nigerian economy and accounted for the major share of its foreign earnings. The manufacturing sector was full of foreign companies of whose interests were to exploit and make use of our raw materials against our industrialization. As such Nigeria inherited a narrow manufacturing sector base preoccupied with the processing of agricultural and forestry contributed only 4.8 percent of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 1960 and

this was associated with institutional impediments which characterized the British colonial administration (Soludo and Adanikiju, 1997). Although not much have been achieved, the Nigerian government initiated import substitution strategy is to prompt rapid development and industrialization. To attain this, government directed its efforts to the expansion of infrastructures which led to the promotion of indigenous and private participation in the manufacturing sector through the Nigeria Enterprises promotion decree (Indigenization, Decree of 1972 and 1977). This period recorded a slight increase in the manufacturing sector to GDP from 4% in 1960 to 7.4% in 1995 (Ogbu, 2012). The Nigerian enterprises promotion Decree of 1972, 1977 and 1981, encouraged growth by limiting foreign ownership in the mid 1970s and late 1980s.

The period of oil Boom (1973 to 1981) accrued high revenue to the government which re-directed government industrial investment from real manufacturing to oil related product manufacturing. According to Englama et al (2010), Nigeria as a result of oil discovery, shifted from its prominent developing industrial production base and placed heavy weight on crude oil production. The country started building refineries, petro-chemical plants etc at the neglect real products manufacturing. Manufacturing sector contribution to Gross Domestic product (GDP) rose from 5.4 in 1980 to 10.7 in 1985 (Ogbu, 2012).

Distortion in global oil prices and inefficient resource allocation led Nigeria to embrace structural adjustment programme to revitalize the recessing economy. Loto (2012), emphasized that Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) was introduced partly to revitalize the manufacturing sector by shifting emphasis to increase domestic sourcing of inputs through monetary and fiscal incentives. At adoption of SAP, the emphasis changed from import substitution strategy to export promotion strategy. This policy allowed foreign investors and private participation in the manufacturing sector of the economy which has evidently shown impact on the economy. The stimulating non-oil export and providing a base for private sector led development was intended to promote industrial efficiency. The period of adjustment reforms and beyond has also featured low capacity utilization in the manufacturing sector, non-competitiveness of export even after the introduction of various export incentive schemes and trade liberalization policy. Recently Nigeria has undertaken reform policies to strengthen the manufacturing sector yet the Nigerian industrial sector, has remained unprovocative. Small and medium industries Equity Investment Scheme of central bank of Nigeria, National Economic Empowerment and Development strategy of 2003 and vision 20/2020 agenda are all policies to engender growth in the Nigerian manufacturing sector. In modest, manufacturing sector contribution in 1960 rose from 4.8% to 7.2% in 1970 and 7.4 in 1975. In 1980, it was 8% and fell to 6.3% in 1997. As at the year 2000, it went down to 3.45 in 2011, it went up to 4.16% till date (CBN,2011). Evidently, Nigerian manufacturing sector has suffered neglect since the country's economy has depended on the petroleum sector since 1970's. Onayemi (2003) lamented that Nigeria is too dependent on oil and it is not progressing significantly due to macro-economic inconsistency, instability, crime and poor security, weak and politicized financial system, poor infrastructure especially electricity and predatory local officials.

2.4 Prospects of Nigeria Manufacturing Industry

Industrialization acts as the catalyst that accelerates the pace of structural transformation and diversification of an economy, enabling the country to fully utilize its factors endowments, depending less on foreign supply of finished goods or raw materials for its economic development and sustainability. The contribution of the manufacturing sector of an economy cannot be overemphasized considering its role in building grounds for development, its employment potentials and financial impact on the economy.

Adenbige (2004) acclaimed that manufacturing industry contributes significantly to the nation's economic development by increasing government revenue through tax, improving standard of living, infrastructure growth, contribution to Gross National Product (GNP), employment

generation and enhancement of manpower development among others. It is also generally agreed that in any economy especially in today's globalised world, manufacturing plays a key role in development.

According to Famade (2009), industrialization is considered as a child of necessity in every nation's economy, for it to accelerate the process of both economic growth and economic development. Thus, the future of every economy lies in its industrial sector which makes it the "heart beat" of economic development. In line with the foregoing, Nigeria in pursuit of rapid industrialization and high productivity has embarked on the following industrial reforms and policies,

- i. Import substitution strategy of 1960
- ii. Nigerian Indigenization policy of 1972 and 1981
- iii. Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) 1966
- iv. Trade and financial liberalization policy (1989)
- v. Bank for industry (BOI, 2000)
- vi. Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS) of 2000
- vii. National Economic Empowerment Development Strategy (NEEDS) 2004.
- viii. And "finally, the millennium vision of 20/2020

2.5 Theoretical Framework

The comparative advantage theory and the factor proportions theory make up the core of the study's theoretical framework, which is trade theory. Trade protectionism and free trade are both examples of the custom union and free trade doctrine. This is done in an effort to highlight the theoretical justifications for protectionism and free trade, respectively.

2.5.1 Trade Theory: The Comparative Advantage Theory

The idea that commerce promotes prosperity and growth has a long history, going all the way back to David Ricardo's concept of political economics from 1817. Akpakpan (1999) explains why nations engage in international commerce despite the fact that its citizens are more adept at manufacturing each and every good than citizens of other nations. David Ricardo, an English political economist, was responding to Adam Smith's absolute advantage hypothesis, a previous idea. The idea was to demonstrate that there was still a foundation for commerce even when one country had a clear advantage in producing every good. According to Ricardo, a condition in which one nation, that is, a situation in which one country had a comparative cost advantage in the production of one item, was essential for comparative advantage to exist. According to him, countries can increase welfare by focusing on producing the goods with the lowest opportunity cost relative to domestic demand, provided that the international rate of exchange between commodities is between the domestic opportunity cost ratios and perfect competition and full resource utilization are assumed.

These benefits are largely static and result from shifting resources from one industry to another as specialization increases based on comparative advantage. The reason for the static advantages from trade is that each nation has a distinct resource endowment, and as a result, each country has a different opportunity cost for manufacturing goods. The marginal rate of transition from one good to another, as shown by the shape of the Production Possibility Curve (PPC), is used to calculate opportunity cost. In other words, how much of one thing must be sacrificed to generate more of the other. According to the rule of comparative advantage, nations will profit if they concentrate on producing the items for which the opportunity cost is lowest and trade those goods for those with greater opportunity costs. That is to say, relative to manufacturing the commodities oneself, the static advantages from trade are assessed by the resource gains to be acquired through exporting to purchase imports more affordably in terms of resources sacrificed. Wall (2000) argued succinctly, that the excess cost of import

substitution, or what is saved by not manufacturing the imported commodities locally, is used to quantify static gains from trade. Increased domestic consumption of both items is just one option for using the resource advantages.

However, if trade is linked to more investments and faster productivity growth based on scale economics, learning by doing, and the acquisition of new knowledge from abroad, particularly through foreign direct investment, then trade's dynamic benefits continually shift outward, expanding the production possibility frontier of nations. The fact that the export market expands the overall market for a country's manufacturers is one of the most important dynamic benefits of trade. Export expansion develops into an ongoing source of productivity growth if output is susceptible to rising returns. Additionally, capital accumulation and rising return are closely related.

2.5.2 The Factor Proportion Theory

Eli Heckscher and Bertil Ohlin, two Swedish economists, initially proposed this hypothesis in 1919 and 1933, respectively. Paul Samuelson later refined it in 1948. It is known as the Heckscher Ohlin-Samuelson hypothesis, or just the H.O.S theory, as a result (Akpakpan, 1999). The factor proportions hypothesis indicates that national production factors play a proportionate role in determining international commerce. According to this idea, disparities in relative factor endowments across nations lead to differences in comparative costs, which in turn lead to differences in trade. This suggests that nations should employ locally plentiful resources to generate export items and buy locally scarce goods. The focus is on the notion that countries should rely on their factor endowments since changes in factor proportions (i.e., factor supply) will result in disparities in relative factor prices, which in turn will cause differences in factor combinations and commodity price ratios. For instance, labor will be relatively inexpensive and will have a relative cost advantage over other nations in the production of goods and services that need abundant labour in a country where capital is scarce but labor is abundant. Therefore, these nations should concentrate on producing labor-intensive products that will offer them surpluses to export in order to cover imports from other nations and vice versa.

The following presumptions form the foundation of this theory: i. There are no transportation costs or trade barriers; ii. The market for factors and commodities is completely competitive; and iii. All production functions are homogeneous and of degree one.

Although the production processes for many commodities vary, they are the same in both nations. Many economists think that the H-O-S theory model or the factor proportions theory model is superior to the Ricardian theory of comparative advantage (Jhingan, 2006). In conclusion, it emphasizes the utilization of their cheap and plentiful production inputs and the importation of goods made using the scarce resources of other nations.

2.5.3 Theory of Custom Union and Free Trade

There have been various initiatives since the conclusion of World War II to encourage commerce by developing worldwide and regional trade agreements in the form of custom of unity and trade liberalization. In a custom union, all tariffs between members are eliminated, and the organization has a uniform external commercial strategy toward non-members. A customs union's main objective is to facilitate free commerce between its member nations. The union promotes international economic cooperation by lowering the administrative and financial costs of trade barriers. The theory of protectionism stands in opposition to this. This theory of trade protection emphasizes how crucial restricted international commerce is to the development of emerging industries and the overall economic progress of developing nations. However, the comparative advantage theory of David Ricardo and an examination of the effects of tariffs or import quotas are two approaches to comprehend the purported benefit of free trade. The theoretical benefits and drawbacks of free trade and protectionism may be demonstrated

using an economic analysis based on the law of supply and demand and the economic impacts of taxation. The rise in trade flows and economic integration are just a couple of the benefits of the Theory of Custom Union to developing nations. A free-trade agreement's primary impact is to promote commerce among its participating nations, assist in better resource allocation that satisfies consumer demands on both the supply and demand sides, and encourage foreign direct investment (FDI).

On the other side, trade diversification and trade creation are used to gauge the customs union's performance. When the union's more effective members sell to its less effective ones, trade is created, which improves the distribution of resources. lowered Trade Deflection once more as One of the primary arguments in favor of a customs union versus a free trade agreement is that the former eliminates the issue of trade diversion.

2.6 Empirical Review

Ogu, Aniebo, and Elekwa (2016) focused on the short to medium-term period while not discounting the extremely significant long-term, which has been the focus of most research, in their investigation of the influence of trade liberalization on the rise of manufacturing output in Nigeria. Manufacturing production, trade openness, per-capita GDP, real interest rates, power generation, export, inflation rate, and bank lending to the manufacturing sector are some of the statistics utilized. Although trade liberalization demonstrated a true potential to increase manufacturing production in the long term, it was proven to damage it in the near term. It was suggested that the competition strategy be overhauled in order to achieve Neutral status in the manufacturing export trade.

Using annual time series data for 1980–2009 and the Ordinary Least Square techniques, Akinmulegun and Olowole (92014) attempted to evaluate the contribution of the manufacturing sector to economic growth in Nigeria in the globalization era. The variables used include data on trade openness and current account balance. The outcome demonstrates that while Nigeria's manufacturing sector benefits from globalization, the industry's degree of growth was determined to be extremely little. That is, the manufacturing sector of the economy experiences little influence from globalization on economic growth.

Umoru and Eborienne (2013) used the human capital model of endogenous growth with modifications for trade liberalization in their research of trade liberalization and industrial growth in Nigeria. The (ECM) results showed that there is a positive and significant correlation between trade and liberalization and industrial growth in Nigeria, that structural deregulation had a positive impact on that growth, that Nigerian industries are labor-intensive, that industrial production responded negatively and insignificantly to capital formation in Nigeria, and that industrial growth is cumulative and self-sustaining in Nigeria. However, the outcome does not show that structural deregulation occurred during the short-run study. Their findings imply that in order to accelerate and sustain industrial growth in Nigeria, the government must start a complete implementation of trade liberalization policies. However, they believed that trade liberalization measures should be implemented slowly and cautiously.

Ashamu and Abiola (2014) looked into how trade with other countries affected the expansion of Nigeria's manufacturing industry. To investigate the long-run dynamic link between a few proxies for international trade on the one hand, and Nigeria's manufacturing sector growth on the other, they used the cointegration and error-correction modeling methodologies. Their research revealed the existence of the long run. In order to estimate a model that attempted to examine the association between trade liberalization and economic development in Nigeria from 1970 to 2012, Olaife et al. (2013) employed the OLS econometric approach. To determine the impact of the free trade policy on the Nigerian economy since it was put into place in 1086, a structural break analysis was also done. The researchers discovered a long-term connection between trade liberalization and economic development. From 1986 to 2012 (the SAP period),

a large structural break was discovered, suggesting that the free trade policy had a significant impact on the Nigerian economy.

Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL), Alwell et al (2017) examined how trade liberalization affected economic development in Nigeria. The study's findings showed that both oil exports and non-oil imports slowed economic development over the long and short terms. Particularly, it was shown that Nigeria's economic development was severely reduced by oil imports. Nigerians import refined petroleum products and spend a significant amount of money doing so.

Titus, Ojeyinka, and Abiodun (2017) studied how trade liberalization affected the performance of the Nigerian economy, paying particular attention to the industrial and agricultural sectors. To represent the combined impact of trade liberalization on the two sectors, simultaneous models were built. The impact of trade liberalization on the performance of the chosen sectors was estimated using the generalized approach of moment methodology. The study demonstrates that trade liberalization has a considerable beneficial influence on the production of the agricultural sector, whereas there is a significant but negative association between trade liberalization measures and industrial output in Nigeria.

Using the Error Correction Trade Approach, Emeremini (2018) examined the effects of trade liberalization on industrial production in Nigeria from 1980 to 2016. The study discovered that trade liberalization has not significantly boosted the growth of the manufacturing sector. The model was developed using manufacturing sector output as the independent variables and trade openness, exchange rate, volume of exports, imports, and balance of payments as the dependent variables. Economic development and trade liberalization were studied by Echekeba, Okonkwo, and Adigwe (2017). Using ordinary least square regression approach, the outcome clearly showed that imports and exports had a large and beneficial impact on Nigeria's economic growth. The study came to the conclusion that trade liberalization benefits the economy of Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study used a time series research approach and relies on secondary data from the NSE reports and the CBN Statistical Bulletin. The research included the years 1981 through 2018. Regression analysis was used in the study as a data analysis technique. However, in order to conduct a full analysis of the properties of time series economic data, it integrates multivariate co-integration and error correction model. The co-integration and error correction model uses four analytical techniques. In order to determine the time series characteristics of the data set and determine the stationary status, the unit root test was first performed for each of the variables. This is required to make sure that the variables are stationary and that shocks are only transient and return to their long-run mean after being dissipated. The test of cointegration is then undertaken to determine the data's long-term rational characteristics. The model's error correction representation, which was obtained in the third stage, was used to assess the model's dynamic short- and long-term behavior.

3.1 Model Specification

In order to effectively capture the impact of trade liberalization and manufacturing sector on the economic growth of Nigeria, it is important to establish a functional model that will help to achieve the major objective of the study. Thus, the model is stated in a functional form as follows:

$$RGDP = f(MAF, EXR, BTR, EXP, IMP, OPN) \quad (1)$$

Where

RGDP= Real Gross Domestic Product

MAF = Manufacturing Rate

EXR = Exchange Rate

BTR = Balance of Trade

EXP= Export value

IMP = Import value

OPN= Trade openness

The econometric form of the model is given as:

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MA_{t-1} + \beta_2 EXR_t + \beta_3 BTR_t + \beta_4 EXP_t + \beta_5 IMP_t + \beta_6 OPN_t + \mu_{1t} \quad (2)$$

Where:

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ = Parameters of the model to be estimated

μ_{1t} = Stochastic error term of the model which accounts for other indices that are not specified in the model

Apriori expectation; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6 > 0$

3.2 Co-integration and Error Correction

Engel and Granger (1987) stated that when two or more non-stationary series are regressed on one another, the residuals from the static regression will be stationary. If so, then there is a long run equilibrium relationship between the series referred to as long run co-integration relationship. In their formulation, Engel and Granger show that, although non-stationarity is a necessary condition for long run Co-integration between the variables, however, for Co-integration to exist there must be a valid error correction mechanism that kept the long run relationship moving together. In addition, Granger and Newbold (1974), argue that if there is valid cointegration relationship between the variables, then the possibility of estimating a spurious (nonsense) regression is ruled out.

Consider a static equation between two $I(1)$ variables which may probably be co integrated:

$$X_t = \alpha + \beta P_t + \eta_t$$

If X_t and P_t are not co-integrated, then there is no possible values of the parameters α and β such that η_t can be stationary. If they are co-integrated however, then, there is a single value for the two parameters such that the linear combination of $X_t = \alpha + \beta P_t + \eta_t$ is stationary. Engel and Granger (1987), shows that if there is evidence of co-integrating relationship between variables; then this relationship can be expressed as error correction mechanisms (ECM). Therefore, while co-integrating vectors represents the long run relationship between non stationary variables that are co integrated; error correction mechanism is the short run property of the variables.

4. RESULT

4.1 Unit Root Test

As mentioned earlier in the previous section, the stationarity or order of integration of the variables is to be determined in order to avoid a spurious regression. The test is carried using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Unit root test and the results are summarized below:

Table 1: Result of ADF Unit Root Test

Variables	Level	First Difference	Order of integration
RGDP	-0.027817	-3.395063	I(1)
MAF	1.046538	-11.73578	I(1)
EXR	3.091041	-3.078498	I(1)
BTR	-9.942254	-6.179269	I(1)
IMP	-1.206720	-6.769921	I(1)
OPN	-1.680574	-7.730308	I(1)
EXP	-1.631686	-5.818661	I(1)
Critical Values	1%	-3.621023	-3.626784
	5%	-2.943427	-2.945842
	10%	-2.610263	-2.611531

The Table 1 above shows the result of the unit root test using the ADF test. It can be seen that in the tests, the t-statistic at first difference are greater than the critical value at 5% meaning that all the variables are stationary at first difference. This also shows that they are all integrated of order I(1). In conclusion, we affirm that the variables have time series statistical properties that are constant hence they do not change over the time period under study.

4.2 Johansen Cointegration Test

The Cointegration test seeks to confirm the long run relationship that exists amongst the variables. Since the variables have stationary process; it is important to ascertain whether the interaction of the independent variables in the long run will affect the dependent variable. The test is summarized below:

Table 2: Johansen Co integration Test Result
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.777687	169.4126	125.6154	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.769562	116.7843	95.75366	0.0008
At most 2	0.534006	65.41212	69.81889	0.1068
At most 3	0.408639	38.68673	47.85613	0.2729
At most 4	0.272878	20.30024	29.79707	0.4027
At most 5	0.149237	9.147088	15.49471	0.3520
At most 6	0.094912	3.490317	3.841466	0.0617

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None*	0.777687	52.62834	46.23142	0.0091
At most 1 *	0.769562	51.37213	40.07757	0.0018
At most 2	0.534006	26.72539	33.87687	0.2783
At most 3	0.408639	18.38649	27.58434	0.4633
At most 4	0.272878	11.15315	21.13162	0.6320
At most 5	0.149237	5.656771	14.26460	0.6576
At most 6	0.094912	3.490317	3.841466	0.0617

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

The trace test indicates that there were 2 co-integrating equations at 0.05 levels. The Max-Eigen value test also indicates 2 co-integrating equations at 0.05 levels. These results showed that the variables are co-integrated. The error correction mechanism result conducted on the specified model is presented on Table 3. The ECM reveals the short run relationship that exists between the dependent variable and each of the explanatory variables.

Table 3: Dependent Variable: RGDP

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	9.283110	0.068768	134.9911	0.0000
EXR	0.000346	0.000551	0.627865	0.5354
BTR	0.027597	0.035873	2.769314	0.0044
EXP	0.149084	0.082342	1.810538	0.0814
IMP	0.032242	0.066199	0.487048	0.6302
MAF	3.30E-05	0.000177	2.186929	0.0031
OPN	-0.015189	0.001645	-9.234145	0.0000
ECM(-1)	-0.592369	0.355690	-4.476844	0.0003

The regression equation above shows that the ECM(-1) is correctly specified. It is negative and statistically significant. This means that it will be effective to correct any deviations from the long-run equilibrium. Moreover, the negative and statistical significance of the ECM confirms that the variables in the model are co-integrated. The coefficient of the ECM(-1) which is -0.592369 indicates that the speed of adjustment to long run equilibrium is 59% percent when any past deviation must be corrected in the present period.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Our findings on the effect of trade liberalization of the manufacturing sector on the Nigeria economic growth have brought to limelight how it as an economic variable relates with the desired growth in the Nigerian economy. The model formulated used RGDP as proxy to economic growth in Nigeria while manufacturing output rate, exchange rate, import and export values, balance of trade and trade openness were the explanatory variables used for manufacturing sector. The variables were standardized by taking the logarithm forms of RGDP, balance of trade, import and export values to avoid a spurious regression. The stationarity of the variables were ascertained using the ADF Unit root test and the result established that the

variables are stationary at first difference. This necessitated the co-integration test for long run relationship amongst the variables and the result indicated that the explanatory (independent) variables have long run relationship with the growth of the Nigerian economy.

The error correction model was used to estimate the coefficients of the parameters. The ECM result revealed that the coefficient of the EXR 0.000346 is positive and statistically insignificant; this means that the EXR impacts positively and is statistically insignificant on the current RGDP. The sign of the coefficient of the EXR in the current period is in conformity with our a priori. The BTR has a negative coefficient of -0.027597 and is statistically significant, this means that the balance of trade relates positively and is statistically significant on the current RGDP. MAF in the current period impacts positively with 3.303205 coefficient and is statistically significant on the current RGDP. Trade openness in the current period impacts negatively with -0.015189 coefficient and is statistically significant on the current RGDP. The import and export values on the other hand have positive relationship with 0.149084 and 0.032242 coefficients respectively, but are statistically insignificant on the current RGDP.

The error correction model coefficient ECM(-1) gave a speed of adjustment of 59% annually. This shows that the model corrects its previous period's disequilibrium at a speed of 59% yearly. The joint significance of the variables were tested using the F-test and the result revealed that the variables jointly relates to economic growth (RGDP) accounting for up to 98% of the variations in real gross domestic product. The Durbin Watson value of 2.349274 shows that the error terms of the model residual are not serially correlated hence the model is free from the problem of autocorrelation.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, though the research evidence has shown mixed findings for several economies, with regards to the Nigeria trade liberalization and manufacturing sector, a key challenge is the deterioration of our exchange rate and the underperformance in our manufacturing productivity sector across the globe which have lost confidence in the system resulting from the unbridled corporate malfeasance on both the manufacturing sector, market operators, management and government at large. There is a need to take steps in restoring this declining confidence in the market. Flowing from the above findings and conclusion drawn, we recommend that there is the need to ensure that the channels of trade liberalization and manufacturing sector productivity induced growth are built around effective systems and that the policy institutions are actively involved in making systemic checks and appropriate policy innovations to ensure trade liberalization and manufacturing productivity sector led economic growth. We also recommend that the relevant regulatory agencies in the exchange rate market should be focused on enhancing the efficiency and transparency of the market in order to improve investor's confidence.

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